

ORGANIC REACTIONS WITH POLYPHOSPHORIC ACID. * PART II. INTERMOLECULAR ACYLATION

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Aromatic hydrocarbons, phenol ethers and alicyclic olefines can be conveniently acylated by various organic acids in the presence of polyphosphoric acid to furnish good yields of the corresponding ketones.

In recent years polyphosphoric acid (PPA) has become increasingly popular for the intramolecular ring-closure of various aryl aliphatic acids (Koebner and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1995; Bachmann and Horton, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 58; Snyder and Werber, *ibid.*, 1950, 72, 2962, 2965; Gilmore and Horton, *ibid.*, 1951, 73, 1411; Horning and Walker, *ibid.*, 1952, 74, 5147; Koo, *ibid.*, 1953, 75, 720; Sukh Dev, this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 789). The use of this reagent has been extended to the cyclisation of alicyclic analogues (Sukh Dev, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 255)*. It was thought of interest to examine the possibility of carrying out intermolecular acylations with the help of PPA, and a preliminary report to that effect was published (*idem.*, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1954, 1071; cf. Gardner, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 4550; Nakazawa and Matsura, *J. Pharm. Soc., Japan*, 1954, 74, 69; Snyder and Elston, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 364). The present communication describes some further work in that direction in order to determine the scope of the reaction.

Acylations of aromatic hydrocarbons and phenol ethers proceed smoothly; since the hydrocarbon component has poor solubility in PPA, the reaction is carried out under relatively forcing conditions; on the other hand in the case of phenol ethers, much milder conditions suffice as a result of their far superior solubility in PPA and enhanced susceptibility to electrophilic substitution. The chief advantage of acylation by the present method lies in the fact that acids can be directly employed as the source of acylium cations (or their equivalent), whereas in the other known methods only acid chlorides or anhydrides can be used (with anhydrous hydrofluoric acid intermolecular acylations with free acids have been carried out: Fieser and Hershberg, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 49; but the reagent is hazardous); in the case of phenol ethers, an additional advantage is the absence of the danger of demethylation. Polyphosphoric acid promises to be especially useful for the acylation of phenol ethers with unsaturated acids. Thus, crotonic acid and anisole furnished *p*-methoxycrotonophenone (I: 80% yield) and with sorbic acid, the corresponding sorbophenone (II: 60% yield) was obtained. The structures of these compounds have been confirmed by (i) light absorption measurements, (ii) oxidation to anisic acid, (iii) quantitative hydrogenation to the saturated ketones and (iv) the identification of the reduced ketones with authentic samples. The simplicity of the preparation of (II) may be contrasted to the method, recently employed by Kuhn and Staab (*Chem. Ber.*, 1954: 87, 262, 266) for the synthesis of sorbophenones and related compounds.

* This paper is also to be regarded as Part I of the present series.

As a result of a systematic study of the reaction of *cyclohexene* with acetic acid, conditions have been worked out, under which Δ^1 -acetyl*cyclohexene* can be conveniently obtained; the procedure appears to offer certain advantages in terms of yield and simplicity of operation over the other methods (Royals and Hendry, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1950, 15, 1151; Cauquill *et al.*, *Bull. soc. chim.*, 1953, 1111; Burton and Praill, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1954, 75; Henne and Tedder, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3628) available for the acetylation of *cyclohexene*. Similarly *cyclopentene* afforded Δ^1 -acetyl*cyclopentene*, but the yield was less satisfactory.

The chief side-reaction responsible for the relatively low yields of the acyl*cyclo*-alkenes is the one leading to the formation of a high-boiling, non-carbonylic, neutral material. It is conceivable that though the polymerisation of the starting olefine can account for a part of this high-boiling residue, a considerable material arises from the carbonium ion (III; or its equivalent) derived from

the enolic form of the unsaturated ketone. It may be noted that in the case of Δ^1 -acetyl*cyclohexene*, this intermediate can, at least partly, lead to the formation of ethylbenzene by an elimination of a proton, followed by rearrangement; and in fact, when the reaction of *cyclohexene* and acetic acid is carried out under more forcing conditions, the yield of ethylbenzene rises rapidly at the expense of the expected Δ^1 -acetyl*cyclohexene*, which in one experiment has been isolated in 38% yield. The formation of aromatic hydrocarbons by the action of phosphorus pentoxide on suitably constituted ketones has been recorded (Kekule and Pott, *Ber.*, 1869, 2, 121; Armstrong and Miller, *Ber.*, 1883, 16, 2259; Frank and Pierle, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 724. Also compare the formation of *m*-cymene by the action of P_2O_5 on the non-enolisable ketone, fenchone: Wallach, *Annalen*, 1895, 234, 324; Lacourt, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belg.*, 1930, 39, 132).

The yields of the various ketones prepared by intermolecular acylation with PPA are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

No.	Starting material.	Acyating acid.	Yield of the ketone.
1	Toluene	Acetic acid	75%
2	Anisole	<i>n</i> -Butyric acid	91
3	"	<i>n</i> -Caproic acid	80
4	"	Crotonic acid	80
5	"	Sorbic acid	60
6	cycloHexene	Acetic acid	50-60
7	cycloPentene	Do	20-27

* E X P E R I M E N T A L

Methyl-p-tolyl Ketone.—To PPA, prepared (Sukh Dev, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 262) from P_2O_5 (70 g.) and syrupy phosphoric acid (85%, 30 c.c.), a mixture of toluene (9.2 g., 0.1 *M*) and acetic acid (6.0 g., 0.1 *M*) was added in one lot. The reaction mixture was vigorously stirred (Hershberg stirrer) and heated at $85^\circ \pm 2^\circ$ (bath temp.) for $2\frac{1}{2}$ hours to the complete exclusion of moisture. The deep brown product, while still hot, was poured on ice-water slurry (about 400 c.c.). When all the complex had decomposed (several hours), the organic material was taken up in ether (40 c.c. $\times$ 3), washed with brine (30 c.c. $\times$ 2) and dried (Na_2SO_4). Removal of the solvent, followed by fractionation, afforded the desired ketone, b. p. $122^\circ/30$ mm., n_D^{26} , 1.5315, yield 10 g. (74.6%).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (HCl method) crystallised from toluene as red needles, m. p. 257° (Allen and Richmond, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1937, 2, 224, record m. p. 258° , cor.).

p-Methoxybutyrophenone.—A mixture of anisole (5.4 g., 0.05 *M*) and *n*-butyric acid (4.4 g., 0.05 *M*) was added to PPA (P_2O_5 , 35 g. and phosphoric acid, 15 c.c.) held at 80° . After stirring and heating at the above temperature for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours, the light brown complex was decomposed as above. The product was extracted with ether (40 c.c. $\times$ 3), washed first with NH_4OH solution (5% ; 40 c.c. $\times$ 2), then with brine (40 c.c. $\times$ 2) and dried (Na_2SO_4). The solvent was removed and the residue fractionated to afford the ketone as a colorless liquid, b. p. $123-24^\circ/0.8$ mm., n_D^{30} 1.5350, m. p. 16° (dip method); λ_{max} (272 μ , ϵ 16,960); yield 8.1 g. (91%) (Skraup and Nieten, *Ber.*, 1924, 57, 1294, record b. p. $165-67^\circ/14$ mm., m. p. 26°).

The semicarbazone was prepared by the pyridine method and after two recrystallisations from dilute alcohol yielded white needles, m. p. $172-73^\circ$. (Found: N, 17.8. $C_{12}H_{17}O_2N_3$ requires N, 17.9 per cent).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (HCl method) was obtained in 95% yield, m. p. $155-57^\circ$. Recrystallisation from acetic acid-alcohol mixture was followed up by another crystallisation from benzene-*n*-hexane, when red lustrous leaflets were obtained, m. p. $165-66^\circ$. (Found: N, 15.5. $C_{17}H_{16}O_6N_4$ requires N, 15.6 per cent).

* All melting and boiling points are uncorrected. The light absorption measurements were carried out in 95% ethanol solution on Beckman DU spectrophotometer.

p-Methoxycaprophenone was prepared as above, using *n*-caproic acid (5.8 g., 0.05 *M*) in place of butyric acid; the reaction complex was dull red in colour. The ketone was purified by distillation, b.p. 145°/0.5 mm., m.p. 37-80°; λ_{max} , 272 m μ (ϵ , 14540); yield 8.0 g. (80%). The product on recrystallisation from *n*-hexane (2 vol.) at 10-0°, furnished white prismatic crystals, m.p. 37-38° (Skraup and Nieten, *loc. cit.*, report m.p. 41°).

The semicarbazone (pyridine method) on two recrystallisations from dilute alcohol furnished white needles, m.p. 128-29°; surprisingly, the crude material had m.p. 133-34°. (Found: N, 16.1. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ requires N, 16.0 per cent).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (HCl method) was prepared quantitatively, m.p. 140-43°. It was obtained as red lustrous leaflets from acetic acid-alcohol mixture or as red tablets from benzene-*n*-hexane, m.p. 146-47°. (Found: N, 14.1. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N}_4$ requires N, 14.5 per cent).

p-Methoxycrotonophenone (I).—To PPA (70 g. P_2O_5 and 30 c.c. phosphoric acid), maintained at $55^\circ \pm 2^\circ$, anisole (10.8 g. 0.1 *M*) and crotonic acid (8.6 g., 0.1 *M*) were added all at once; the mixture was heated and stirred for 40 minutes. The deep red product was worked up as above. The ketone was obtained as a colorless liquid, b.p. 143-45°/3 mm., n_D^{20} , 1.5780; m.p. 20-21° (dip method); yield, 14.0 g. (80%). (Found: C, 75.00; H, 6.82. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 75.00; H, 6.81 per cent).

The 2:4 dinitrophenylhydrazone (HCl method) was obtained quantitatively and had m.p. 129-30°; it appeared to be a mixture of isomers. Three recrystallisations from acetic acid-alcohol furnished small deep red needles, m.p. 186-87°. (Found: N, 15.5. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2\text{N}_4$ requires N, 15.7 per cent).

The structure of the ketone is based on the following experiments:

(i) Light absorption: λ_{max} , 295 m μ (ϵ , 14,690) (Kuhn and Staab, *loc. cit.*, record λ_{max} 252, ϵ 17.5×10^3 for crotonophenone); besides this main band, it had; λ_{max} , 229 m μ (ϵ 12030) and λ_{max} , 255 m μ (ϵ 7750).

(ii) To the compound (0.88 g.) in acetone (25 c.c.) and water (25 c.c.), powdered KMnO_4 was added in small lots with stirring; the second addition was made only when the first had been consumed; the oxidation was carried out at room temperature (28°) and was quite rapid. It required 2.8 g. of KMnO_4 during $\frac{1}{2}$ hour; the slight excess of it was destroyed with a trace of crotonic acid. The manganese dioxide was filtered off and washed with hot water (15 c.c.). The alkaline solution was concentrated to about 25 c.c. and acidified and the precipitated acid collected, m.p. 180-82° with previous shrinking; yield 0.5 g. Recrystallisation from dilute acetic acid afforded long needles of *anisic acid*, m.p. 183-84°; mixed m.p. with an authentic sample remained undepressed.

(iii) The ketone (0.6 g.) in alcohol (20 c.c.) on quantitative hydrogenation in presence of pre-reduced Pd- CaCO_3 catalyst (300 mg., Busch, *Ber.*, 1916, 49, 1063; 1929, 62, 1458) took up 101% of the theoretical amount of hydrogen (required for the saturation of one ethylenic linkage) during 10 minutes when the reduction came to a close. On being worked up in the usual manner, an oil (520 mg.), b.p. 105-110°/0.2 mm., n_D^{20} , 1.5330, was obtained. It was identified as *p*-methoxybutyropenone by the m.p. (165-66°) and mixed m.p. of its 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone.

p-Methoxysorbophenone.—A mixture of sorbic acid (5.6 g., 0.05 *M*; finely powdered) ("Organic Syntheses", vol. 24, p. 92; Miller and Nord, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1951, 16, 1720), anisole (5.4 g., 0.05 *M*) and PPA (70 g. of P_2O_5 and 30 c.c. of phosphoric acid) was stirred and heated at $55^\circ \pm 2^\circ$ for 30 minutes under the usual conditions. The deep blood-red complex was at once decomposed with ice-water slurry (about 400 c.c.) with the separation of a solid. The product was extracted first with benzene (50 c.c. $\times$ 1) and then with ether (50 c.c. $\times$ 2); the combined extracts were washed, etc. as above. The solvent was removed and the crude material rapidly distilled from a flask suitable for the distillation of solids; the light yellow distillate, b.p. $160^\circ\text{--}65^\circ/0.3$ mm., solidified as it distilled, m.p. $62\text{--}89^\circ$, yield 6.0 g. (60%). It crystallised from benzene-*n*-hexane as dull yellow prisms, m.p. $92\text{--}93^\circ$. (Found: C, 77.15; H, 6.91. $C_{19}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 77.22; H, 6.93 per cent).

Its 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (HCl method) after two recrystallisations from acetic acid-alcohol mixture was obtained as dark-red, bright needles, m.p. $194\text{--}95^\circ$ (the crude material, which was obtained in 97% yield, had m.p. $155\text{--}62^\circ$ and was evidently a mixture of isomers). (Found: N, 14.8. $C_{19}H_{14}O_8N_4$ requires N, 14.7 per cent).

The ketone had λ_{max} 315 $m\mu$ (ϵ 30,560). On oxidation with $KMnO_4$ as above, it (100 mg.) yielded anisic acid (55 mg., m.p. $183\text{--}84^\circ$). On quantitative hydrogenation in the manner described above, it showed the presence of two easily reducible (reduction came to a close after 10 minutes) ethylenic linkages; the tetrahydroketone was identified as *p*-methoxycaprophenone through its 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic sample, $144\text{--}45^\circ$).

Δ^1 -Acetylcyclohexene.—To PPA (from 70 g. of P_2O_5 and 30 c.c. of phosphoric acid), held at $55^\circ\text{--}60^\circ$ (bath temp.), cyclohexene (8.2 g., 0.1 *M*) and acetic acid (6.6 g., 0.11 *M*) were introduced all at once. The reaction mixture was efficiently stirred and heated at this temperature for just 45 minutes. The dark brown-red product was at once worked up by pouring the material on ice-water slurry (about 400 c.c.); after decomposition of the complex, the mixture was further diluted to a total volume of about 500 c.c., and ammonium sulphate (200 g.) added and dissolved. This was extracted with petroleum ether (40 c.c. $\times$ 5), washed with brine (40 c.c. $\times$ 2) and dried (Na_2SO_4). This was stripped off (column) the solvent and the residue fractionated to furnish 6.2-7.5 g. (50-60.2 %) of acetylcyclohexene, b.p. $104\text{--}105^\circ/35$ mm., n_D^{20} , 1.4890. After refractionation the product had b.p. $101^\circ\text{--}103^\circ/30$ mm., n_D^{20} , 1.4880; λ_{max} , 233 $m\mu$ (ϵ 11,060) (Heilbron *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1827 record λ_{max}^{EtOH} , 232 $m\mu$, ϵ 13,000). The ketone was further characterised by the preparation of its 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. $203\text{--}204^\circ$ (brick-red needles from alcohol; Heilmann and Glenat, *Compt. rend.*, 1952, 284, 1557, record m.p. 204° corr.) and semicarbazone, m.p. $218\text{--}19^\circ$ (colorless leaflets from dilute alcohol; Nenitzescu and Chicco, *Ber.*, 1933, 66, 969, report m.p. $220\text{--}21^\circ$ with decomposition).

Δ^1 -Acetylcyclopentene.—cyclopentene (6.8 g., 0.1 *M*; Sukh Dev, unpublished) and acetic acid (6.6 g., 0.11 *M*) were treated with PPA as above, but the temperature was maintained at $40^\circ \pm 1^\circ$. On working up the dark brown-red complex in the above

manner, acetylcyclopentene (3 g., 27% ; refractionated), b.p. 80-82°/30 mm., was obtained. The product had n_D^{25} , 1.4825, appreciably higher than the value (n_D^{25} 1.4776) reported by Heilbron *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) ; it had λ_{max} , 237 m μ (ϵ 9,800) (Heilbron *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, record λ_{max} , 239 m μ ; ϵ 13,000). It afforded 2:4 dinitrophenylhydrazone, which separated from alcohol in red needles, m.p. 202-203° (Heilbron *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, record m.p. 203°).

Isolation of Ethylbenzene.—To PPA (P₂O₅, 200 g. and phosphoric acid, 120 c.c.) cyclohexene (41.0 g., 0.5 M) and acetic anhydride (51.0 g., 0.5 M) were added and vigorously stirred at 50° for $\frac{1}{2}$ an hour at 60°-70° for one hour and finally at 80°-85° for another 1 $\frac{1}{2}$ hours. The product was worked up as given under Δ^1 -acetylcyclohexene (there was a lot of tarry material, insoluble in petroleum ether ; this was rejected). On fractionation, the crude product provided two main fractions (i) b.p. 55°/40 mm., 20 g. and (ii) b.p. 112°-118°/40 mm., 6 g., and a polymerised residue (23 g.) was left behind. The second fraction consisted essentially of acetylcyclohexene. The first fraction was refractionated over sodium: b.p. 130°/684 mm., n_D^{25} 1.4900; yield 19 g. [Huntress and Mulliken, "Identification of Pure Organic Compounds. Order I", John Wiley, New York, 1946, p. 520, record b.p. 136.15°/760 mm., n_D^{25} 1.4958; n_D^{25} , 1.4931 for ethylbenzene].

The product had a typical odour recalling toluene ; it did not decolorise bromine in the cold and it developed a faint yellowish colour with tetranitromethane.

When the hydrocarbon (1 g.) was oxidised by refluxing with KMnO₄ (8 g. in 160 c.c. of water containing 1 g. of NaOH), benzoic acid (m.p. 119-120°, mixed m.p. 120-122° ; 150 mg.) was isolated.

Its identification as ethylbenzene was completed by the Friedel-Crafts condensation (Shriner and Fuson, "The Systematic Identification of Organic Compounds", John Wiley, New York, 1948, p. 198) with phthalic anhydride, when *O*-(4-ethylbenzoyl)-benzoic acid, m.p. 123-25° (white needles recrystallised first from benzene-*n*-hexane and then from dilute acetic acid) was isolated ; mixed m.p. with an authentic sample (m.p. 123-25°) remained undepressed.